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**ZBORNIK RADOVA
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THE EFFECT OF TREHALOSE/HYALURONATE EYE DROPS IN GLAUCOMA PATIENTS WITH MILD TO MODERATE DRY EYE SYMPTOMS

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Abstract

Introduction: Dry eye symptoms frequently coexist with glaucoma and may be initiated or exacerbated by topical glaucoma medications. Thealoz Duo® is a novel artificial tear preparation containing two active ingredients: trehalose, a natural alpha-linked disaccharide with high water retention capabilities and sodium hyaluronate, an anionic glycosaminoglycan polysaccharide found in various connective tissues which has lubricant and water-retaining properties.

Aim: The aim of our study was to evaluate the efficacy of trehalose/hyaluronate eye drops (Thealoz Duo®) in recovering tear film changes in glaucoma patients with mild to moderate dry eye symptoms.

Methodology and results: The group of glaucoma patients (n=30, 14 males and 16 females) under topical medical treatment and age-matched controls (n=30, 12 males and 18 females) were reviewed. The mean age of all patients was 56.3±15.9 years, 26 males and 34 females. Age, gender, number of glaucoma medications used, the duration of glaucoma treatment and the presence of dry eye symptoms were recorded. After initial evaluation, patients were instructed to administer Thealoz Duo® with the regimen of one drop/eye/three times daily. Patients were observed in 2 visits: day 0 (baseline) and after three months of treatment (endpoint). Tear film quality was measured using tear break-up time (TBUT) test. Significant changes at the endpoint as compared to the baseline were found in both groups (p<0,05). TBUT results improved in both, glaucoma (7,33±3,90 vs. 8,08±3,88 seconds) and non-glaucoma (8,36±3,66 vs. 8,80±3,47 seconds) patients.

Conclusion: The improvement in tear film quality (measured by TBUT test) was shown after application of trehalose/hyaluronate eye drops for three months in both, glaucoma and control group patients with mild to moderate dry eye symptoms. However, randomized studies are required to truly ascertain the magnitude of their clinical value.

Key words: dry eye, glaucoma patients, trehalose/hyaluronate eye drops

DELAYED TREATMENT AND VISUAL OUTCOMES IN PATIENTS WITH CAROTICO-CAVERNOUS FISTULE DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC: TWO CASE REPORTS

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Abstract

Introduction: Carotid-cavernous fistula (CCF) is a form of abnormal communication between carotid arterial system and cavernous sinus. While direct CCFs are more likely to be traumatic, indirect fistulas most commonly occur spontaneously.

Case reports: A 75-year-old man was referred to the hospital in November 2021 due to the visual loss followed by ophthalmoplegia and increasing eyelid swelling on the right eye (RE). He had COVID-19 pneumonia in September 2021. There was both upper and lower eyelid swelling followed by upper eyelid ptosis and conjunctival chemosis in the RE. Eye movements were restricted in all directions of gaze and proptosis was present. Relative afferent pupillary defect (RAPD) was positive with no light perception in the RE. Digital subtraction angiography (DSA) showed diffuse atherosclerotic changes in a form of alternating segmental dilatation and stenosis located in both intra and extracranial parts of the internal carotid artery. At a 4-month follow up examination, a resolution of proptosis and a gradual improvement in ophthalmoplegia were present, however visual loss remains. Second case is about 85-year-old woman who was referred to the hospital in March 2022 due to the visual loss and pain during left eye (LE) movement. She had COVID-19 pneumonia in January 2022 followed by thrombophlebitis in the left leg. Anterior segment examination revealed proptosis, semiptosis of the upper eyelid and a narrow anterior chamber on the LE. RAPD was negative with preserved light perception on the LE. DSA showed small indirect CCF which was already partially closed therefore it was not surgically addressed. At a 3-month follow up examination, a resolution of proptosis was observed however visual acuity remains the same.

Conclusion: CCF should be added into differential diagnosis as a cause of visual loss in COVID-19 patients since prompt diagnosis and proper treatment may result in a better visual outcome and prognosis.

Key words: carotid-cavernous fistula, delayed treatment, COVID-19 pandemic

ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES ON THE OPTIC NERVE HEAD AND RETINAL NERVE FIBER LAYER IN PATIENTS WITH PRIMARY OPEN ANGLE GLAUCOMA USING SPECTRAL DOMAIN OPTICAL COHERENCE TOMOGRAPHY

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Abstract

Introduction: Changes in the retinal nerve fibre layer (RNFL) are one of the most important findings for the early diagnosis and determination of glaucoma progression.

Aim: The aim of our study was to assess structural changes on the optic nerve head (ONH) and RNFL in patients with primary open angle glaucoma (POAG) and to compare them with healthy controls using spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT).

Methods: This study included 60 eyes from 18 POAG patients and 15 healthy controls. ONH and RNFL analysis were performed in all patients. Rim area, disc area, average cup/disc (C/D) ratio, vertical C/D ratio, cup volume data, average RNFL thickness and RNFL thickness in all four quadrants (superior, inferior, nasal and temporal) were assessed using SD-OCT. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS25.0, and the difference was considered significant if $p < 0.05$. All values are expressed as means \pm SD.

Results: The mean age of all patients was 59.73 ± 18.55 years. Statistically significant difference between healthy controls and POAG group was established in the rim area (1.517 ± 0.384 vs. 1.075 ± 0.390), average C/D ratio (0.343 ± 0.129 vs. 0.550 ± 0.172), vertical C/D ratio (0.542 ± 0.127 vs. 0.727 ± 0.142), horizontal C/D ratio (0.619 ± 0.152 vs. 0.789 ± 0.143), cup volume (0.206 ± 0.163 vs. 0.449 ± 0.310) and average RNFL thickness (101.63 ± 8.97 vs. 82.46 ± 14.03). Significant difference was also observed in the superior (123.66 ± 13.37 vs. 99.96 ± 18.91), inferior (125.63 ± 13.10 vs. 99.06 ± 23.04) and nasal (82.60 ± 9.13 vs. 68.76 ± 12.33) quadrant thickness. Significant difference related to the disc area and temporal quadrant thickness between healthy controls and POAG group was not observed ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: SD-OCT technology provides valuable measurements of different retinal and optic nerve structures, which in combination with functional assessment can more objectively differentiate normal from glaucomatous eyes and more precisely detect glaucoma progression.

Key words: primary open angle glaucoma, glaucoma progression, SD-OCT, RNFL thickness

ORBITAL RETINOBLASTOMA IN A 2-YEAR-OLD: CASE REPORT

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Abstract

Introduction: Clinically, radiologically, or histopathologically detected extension of retinoblastoma outside the confines of the eye is termed as orbital retinoblastoma. Based on the clinicopathological presentation it is divided into primary and secondary (accidental, microscopic and overt) orbital retinoblastoma. Delayed detection and inappropriate management of the orbital extension contribute to the poor outcome and higher mortality rate.

Case report: We present a case of a 2-year-old boy who was admitted to the University Clinical Centre of Serbia Eye Hospital in May last year, because of left eye leucocoria (LE). Ultrasonography and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) followed by the fundus examination of the affected eye showed an intraocular tumor presenting calcification compatible with retinoblastoma. Primary enucleation was the treatment of choice. The pathohistological examination of the enucleated eye showed no high-risk histopathology features. Therefore, no adjuvant chemotherapy or radiotherapy was indicated. Three months after the enucleation, patient returned with massive orbital recurrence and prosthesis-fitting problem. The MRI finding was consistent with tumor recurrence, which was confirmed by the excisional biopsy and subsequent histopathological analysis (immunohistology and molecular genetics). The patient was then subjected to 12 cycles of high-doses chemotherapy with vincristine sulfate, etoposide phosphate and carboplatin followed by the 45Gy of external beam radiotherapy in 25 fractions.

Conclusion: Although each clinical situation is unique with a gross variation in tumor load, the currently preferred management is multimodal with a combination of chemotherapy, surgery, and external beam radiotherapy, with an excellent prognosis for patient survival.

Key words: orbital retinoblastoma, management, delayed detection